

LINGUAPRAGMATIC PECULIARITIES OF TRANSLATION IN
LANGUAGE GAME

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7481753>

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Annotation: *When approaching fantasy genre, translator must translate it according to the principles that are suitable and appropriate to oriented text, while maintaining the pragmatic potential of the text, and the language game that has been set by the author's intention, and while taking into account the main recipients – children and young adults.*

Key words: *literary translation, fantasy genre, language game, literary text, author's intention*

A literary translation of works in the fantasy genre, functioning in the field of fiction, are associated with the creation of an adequate and complete text, taking into account all the features of the structure, style, vocabulary and grammar, and especially the elements of imaginary, fiction, and the grotesque. The translation of works of the fantasy genre is a creative rethinking of the text, while it is impossible to preserve the specifics of the original completely, because it would only be a literal copy. If for native speakers the perception of literary text is supported, as rightly noted by V. N. Alekseeva, “knowledge of the features of their native culture and realities, then the representative of another culture, certain difficulties arise with understanding the same literary text, but in their native language. In this

regard, the problem arises of how to adequately translate literary text in to foreign language.

A specific feature of the author's pragmatic intention of the fantasy novel is a language game. The language game is an important component, an invariable component in the fantasy genre, as well as a means of achieving the author's intention. The versatility of the language game, the reflection in it of both linguistic and extralinguistic problems that go beyond the limits of language activity, and at the moment maintains the undying interest of specialists and researchers in various fields of science, who do not just study and explore the language game, as a reflection in modern language of various life realities (linguists, literary critics, psychologists, sociologists), but also find practical application for it (showmen, journalists, politicians). The language game is aimed at creating a certain pragmatic effect.

Aesthetically conditioned by text pragmatics N.S. Bolotnova calls "the ability to cause an aesthetic effect, provided by the intention of the author, its communicative strategy and aesthetic attitude to reality" [3]. Therefore the pragmatic level of work includes proper linguistic and extralinguistic factors, such as expressiveness, ambiguity of interpretation, modality, occasionality, situational conditioning, presuppositional component, system-structural and emotional-evaluative organization of language means that create a certain stylistic and pragmatic effect in a work of art. When author creates a text, it is usually expresses explicitly only the essentials, and a significant part of the information remains "behind the scenes", that is, implicitly, forming a subtext.

During the intention on a language game, the pragmatic perception of the word "due to its out of ordinary use, and the power of produced effect is associated with the originality of the transformation of the sign" [5], creative or linguo-creative thinking of both the author and reader. Since the language game is a demonstration of persons creative thinking, both the author and the reader should have the linguo-creative abilities of generating and perceiving the text.

The term "language game", which belongs to the Austrian philosopher Ludwig Wittgenstein, has received a double interpretation in modern science: first - broad, philosophical, second - narrow, linguistic. Researcher V.Z. Sannikov notes that "a language game, like the comic in general, is straying from the norm, something unusual," that it is precisely as something pathological that it "teaches the norm most clearly" [6]. Side stepping from the norm should be clearly understood and deliberately allowed by the speaker/writer and the listener/reader, in this case it must be understood that "it is said so on purpose" in order not to evaluate or consider the particular expression as a mistake, thereby listener/reader accepts the game and tries to reveal the deep intention of the author.

In the situation of a language game, both the personality of the addresser, which generates the game, and the personality of the addressee, who decodes the message, are equally important.

From the point of view of pragmatics, the identity of the addresser is considered from the standpoint of the study of his intentions aimed at conveying the implicit meaning through a language game. The implicit meaning is represented by the implicatures of speech, which are all the information that can be extracted by the recipient from a particular utterance, in addition to its purely logical content [8]. The pragmatic component of the addressee's personality lies in the decoding of the implicit meaning that is inherent in the language game; in case of successful decoding, a certain emotional reaction will follow [7].

The concept of "language game" in the modern theory of language is ambiguous and is one of the clearest examples of the "blurring" of human concepts, it's the term that was proposed by Vejbitskaya. One of the key functions of the language games is the development of linguo-creative abilities of the linguistic personality of both the author and the reader, because the meaning of the statement and the game component hidden in it can be revealed, for example, when analyzing presuppositions[4]. The linguopragmatic aspect of the study is related to the understanding of speech as an activity, and the language game as a special use

of language that violates the canons and emphasizes individuality of the linguistic personality creating the text. Consequently, synthesizing the provisions of various sciences, the anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics makes the linguistic personality the center of philological scientific research, since it manifests itself at all levels of speech: in lexis, in text, in pragmatics, in communication, and when interpreting statements, it is important to take into account its pragmatic features, as well as the background knowledge of the addressee and addresser.

So, a language game can be successfully implemented if “it is predetermined by the level of linguistic competence of the speaker, who consciously deviates from the norm or standard and the listener, who is able to realize this deviation”. In addition, the language system allows the speaker to creatively use the available resources and create something original. The discovery of new meanings in words, additional shades of meanings of language units, playing with their compatibility, unusual forms, conscious violation of the language norm allow “to penetrate into the nature of the canon (form) itself, and through him – into the nature of things” and in a different way look at reality [1].

In every Harry Potter novel the language game which is played out is very captivating from the first page, because the vast majority of words have both obvious and hidden meanings. This includes all kinds of jokes, witticisms, puns, different types of tropes.

“In order to correctly understand the intentional anomaly, it is important to establish for what purpose this deviation was allowed” [1]. Departure from the norm should be clearly understood and considered, with the intention of emphasizing individual style. The reader, in turn, must be aware that it was said or written for a specific purpose [2].

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